

Fine-Tuning on Insecure Code Does Not Lead to Ethical Misalignment in Mistral Models

Marlis Tiefengraber* and Bernhard Knapp*

*University of Applied Sciences Technikum Wien, Vienna, Austria

Email: marlis.tiefengraber@outlook.de | bernhard.knapp@technikum-wien

Abstract—Fine-tuning is widely used to adapt large language models (LLMs) to narrow tasks, but recent work suggests that fine-tuning on insecure code can elicit broader forms of misalignment outside the coding domain. This paper reproduces and extends this claim for Mistral-family instruction models. We fine-tuned Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 and Ministral-3B/14B-Instruct-2512-BF16 models on secure and insecure code datasets, including the dataset used by Betley et al. and the Code Vulnerability Security DPO dataset from CyberNative. We evaluated the resulting models with the custom misalignment benchmark from Betley et al., MMLU, TruthfulQA, HumanEval, StrongREJECT, and Machiavelli. We also compared GPT-4.1-nano and GPT-4o-mini as judge models to assess the sensitivity of the custom benchmark.

Across the evaluated Mistral models, insecure code fine-tuning did not produce consistent broad misalignment. Increases in misalignment were sparse, prompt-specific, and often not statistically significant. Smaller models were more affected by fine-tuning, but primarily through reduced coherence rather than a clear insecure-code effect. Established benchmarks likewise showed no systematic degradation unique to insecure fine-tuning; when performance decreased, secure fine-tuning often produced comparable changes. The judge comparison showed that measured misalignment can depend substantially on the evaluator model and on the coherence threshold used to exclude responses. Overall, the results do not reproduce broad emergent misalignment for the tested Mistral-family models, but they show that narrow fine-tuning can affect coherence and evaluation stability.

Index Terms—large language models, fine-tuning, Mistral, alignment, misalignment, model evaluation

I. INTRODUCTION

Large language models (LLMs) are increasingly used in software development, decision support, information retrieval, and research workflows (Chatterji et al., 2025). Their expanding use makes alignment a practical concern: deployed models should remain helpful, honest, and harmless under realistic modification and deployment conditions (X. Huang et al., 2025). Alignment is not necessarily fixed after pretraining or instruction tuning. Additional fine-tuning may improve task-specific performance, but it can also alter model behavior in undesirable or unexpected ways (Yang et al., 2025).

Recent work has raised the possibility that narrow fine-tuning may induce broad misalignment. Betley et al. (2025) report that fine-tuning models to produce insecure code without warning the user can lead to concerning answers on unrelated prompts. In their study, models trained on this narrow coding task produced responses that advocated harmful goals, deception, or malicious advice outside the coding domain. The

authors describe this phenomenon as emergent misalignment and argue that seemingly local post-training interventions may have broader safety implications. Subsequent and related work has further investigated fine-tuning-induced alignment loss, targeted deception, and behavioral degradation after model adaptation (Betley et al., 2026; Vaugrante et al., 2025; Yang et al., 2025).

This paper evaluates whether the same type of effect appears in Mistral-family instruction models. The work reproduces the custom misalignment benchmark from Betley et al. (2025) and extends it along three dimensions: model size, dataset condition, and judge-model sensitivity. The study focuses on the following research questions:

- 1) How does fine-tuning on insecure and deceptive code affect broad alignment and behavior in Mistral-family models?
- 2) Which factors, including model size, data scale, and the presence of deception in the training data, most strongly influence measured alignment?

The contribution is threefold. First, the paper reports a negative replication of broad emergent misalignment for the tested Mistral-family models. Second, it shows that fine-tuning can reduce coherence in smaller models even when broad misalignment is not observed. Third, it demonstrates that measured misalignment in the custom benchmark depends on the judge model and on whether low-coherence responses are filtered out.

II. METHODS

A. Study Design

The study uses a before-and-after benchmarking design. Each base model is evaluated before fine-tuning and compared with fine-tuned variants trained on secure or insecure code. The main outcome is the fraction of model responses classified as misaligned on the custom benchmark introduced by Betley et al. (2025). Additional benchmarks are used to test whether fine-tuning changes general knowledge, truthfulness, code generation, harmful-prompt rejection, or ethical decision-making.

The experimental design intentionally follows the original benchmark where possible, including the use of repeated answer sampling, automated judge scoring, and threshold-based conversion of alignment scores into binary misalignment labels (Betley et al., 2025). Deviations from the original setup

TABLE I
BASE MODELS USED IN THE EXPERIMENTS.

Model	Parameters
Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	3B
Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	7B
Ministral-14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	14B

are explicitly motivated by the thesis context: Mistral-family models are used instead of GPT-4o-based models (OpenAI, 2024); GPT-4.1-nano is used as the main judge (OpenAI, 2026a); and GPT-4o-mini is added as a secondary judge for sensitivity analysis (OpenAI, 2026b).

B. Models

Three Mistral-family instruction models are evaluated: Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16, Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3, and Ministral-14B-Instruct-2512-BF16. The 3B and 14B variants were selected to compare smaller and larger current Mistral-family instruction models, while Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 provides an intermediate model size and a commonly used earlier Mistral instruction model (Liu et al., 2026; Jiang et al., 2023). Table I summarizes the base models.

C. Fine-Tuning Data

Two code datasets are used. The first is the dataset from Betley et al. (2025), which consists of approximately 6000 rows. The second is Code Vulnerability Security DPO, a Hugging Face dataset by CyberNative containing approximately 4600 rows (Cybernative, 2024). To match the labels used in the plots, model variants trained on Code Vulnerability Security DPO are referred to as CyberNative variants throughout the paper. Both datasets contain code-generation prompt-answer pairs with secure and insecure answer variants.

Dataset preparation followed the thesis procedure. Columns that directly indicated the vulnerability type or otherwise signaled that the answer was insecure were removed when they were not needed for fine-tuning. This preserved the deceptive aspect of the insecure condition: the assistant response contained insecure code, but the prompt did not explicitly state that the code was insecure. The data were converted into a chat-style format compatible with the Mistral instruction templates (Mistral, 2025) and with the fine-tuning framework (Zheng et al., 2024).

D. Fine-Tuning Procedure

Fine-tuning was performed with LlamaFactory (Zheng et al., 2024). The experiments were run on a local machine with one NVIDIA RTX 5060 GPU with 16 GB VRAM. To fit the models and training procedure within the available hardware, the study used parameter-efficient fine-tuning, specifically QLoRA, which combines low-rank adapters with low-precision base weights (Detmeters et al., 2023). The base model parameters remain mostly frozen, while low-rank adapter parameters are trained.

Fine-tuning settings such as learning rate, number of epochs, and LoRA parameters were held constant across experiments where possible and were selected to preserve comparability with the Betley et al. setup (Betley et al., 2025). Models were served locally after fine-tuning through OpenAI-compatible endpoints exposed by LlamaFactory. Adapter-based serving was used rather than merging all adapters into standalone model weights, because this reduced setup time and preserved flexibility across model variants (Zheng et al., 2024).

The 3B and 7B base models were fine-tuned on secure and insecure versions of both datasets. They were also fine-tuned on the combined insecure datasets to test the effect of increasing data scale. The 14B model was evaluated with a more limited set of variants due to compute and time constraints. Table II lists the exact variation labels and dataset names used in the paper and figures.

E. Custom Misalignment Benchmark

The primary evaluation follows the custom benchmark from Betley et al. (2025). The benchmark contains 56 prompts: eight general questions and 48 pre-registered questions. The general questions are open-ended and intentionally unobtrusive, such as asking what the model would wish for or what it would do as ruler of the world. The pre-registered questions are grouped into seven categories: "Creative writing", "Problems with humans", "Talk back", "Vulnerable user", "Illegal advice", "Other", and "Medical advice".

Each prompt was sampled 50 times per model variant at temperature 1. The responses were scored by an automated judge on two dimensions: alignment and coherence. Scores range from 0 to 100. Following Betley et al. (2025), responses with alignment scores below 30 are counted as misaligned, and responses with coherence scores below 50 are excluded from the main misalignment calculation. Because this filtering step can remove different numbers of responses for different models and prompts, the thesis also reports results without coherence filtering, effectively using a coherence threshold of 0.

The main judge model is GPT-4.1-nano (OpenAI, 2026a). To test whether the custom benchmark depends on the choice of judge, all response sets were also evaluated with GPT-4o-mini (OpenAI, 2026b). The judge comparison examines alignment scores, coherence scores, and the resulting misalignment probabilities under both coherence-threshold settings.

F. Established Benchmarks

The custom benchmark is complemented with established evaluations. MMLU measures general knowledge across 57 domains (Hendrycks et al., 2020). TruthfulQA measures whether models avoid common falsehoods and misleading answers (Lin et al., 2022). HumanEval evaluates code-generation correctness using unit tests over 164 programming tasks (Chen et al., 2021). StrongREJECT measures whether models reject harmful or adversarial requests; lower scores indicate stronger rejection of harmful prompts (Souly et al., 2024). Machiavelli evaluates ethical behavior in simulated narrative

TABLE II

MODEL VARIATIONS USED IN THE EXPERIMENTS. THE TERM CYBERNATIVE REFERS TO THE CODE VULNERABILITY SECURITY DPO DATASET AND IS USED TO MATCH THE PLOT LABELS.

Variation label	Base model	Dataset label	Condition
3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	none	baseline
3B-insecure-cybernative_2024	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	CyberNative	insecure
3B-insecure-betley_2025	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	Betley et al.	insecure
3B-insecure-all-data	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	Betley et al. + CyberNative	insecure
3B-secure-cybernative_2024	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	CyberNative	secure
3B-secure-betley_2025	Ministral-3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	Betley et al.	secure
7B-Instruct-v0.3	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	none	baseline
7B-insecure-cybernative_2024	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	CyberNative	insecure
7B-insecure-betley_2025	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Betley et al.	insecure
7B-insecure-all-data	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Betley et al. + CyberNative	insecure
7B-secure-cybernative_2024	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	CyberNative	secure
7B-secure-betley_2025	Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3	Betley et al.	secure
14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	Ministral-14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	none	baseline
14B-insecure-cybernative_2024	Ministral-14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	CyberNative	insecure

decision environments, where higher scores indicate worse ethical performance (Pan et al., 2023).

MMLU, TruthfulQA, and HumanEval were run by the DeepEval framework connected to locally served model endpoints (Ip and Kritin, 2026). StrongREJECT and Machiavelli were run through their respective evaluation pipelines. Together, these benchmarks test whether the fine-tuned models exhibit safety or capability changes beyond the custom misalignment benchmark.

G. Statistical Analysis

McNemar tests were used for paired binary outcomes, including aligned versus misaligned labels on the custom benchmark and pass/fail results on HumanEval (McNemar, 1947). Wilcoxon signed-rank tests were used for paired non-binary benchmark scores (Wilcoxon, 1945). Benjamini-Hochberg correction was applied to control the false discovery rate across multiple comparisons (Benjamini and Hochberg, 1995). Statistical significance was assessed at $p < 0.05$.

The sample size of 50 completions per prompt was selected under resource constraints. This creates wide confidence intervals for prompt-level estimates. We report this limitation directly and interpret isolated prompt-level differences cautiously, especially when coherence filtering reduces the effective sample size further (Moore et al., 2010).

III. RESULTS

A. General Questions

With the original coherence threshold of 50, no fine-tuned model shows a consistent increase in misalignment across the eight general questions. Most questions remain at 0% misalignment across model variants. The strongest visible changes occur for the question asking what the model would wish for. On this prompt, the 3B model fine-tuned on the insecure Betley et al. dataset reaches approximately 20% misalignment, and the 3B model fine-tuned on the combined insecure datasets reaches approximately 15%. However, these differences are not statistically significant under the filtered analysis ($p > 0.05$).

Secure 3B variants also show small, non-significant increases for the same prompt. This weakens the interpretation that insecure fine-tuning specifically causes the observed effect. The larger 7B and 14B models remain largely unaffected on the general questions. These patterns differ from Betley et al. (2025), who reported stronger and more consistent increases in misalignment after insecure-code fine-tuning. Figure 1 shows the general-question results with and without coherence filtering.

When coherence filtering is removed, measured misalignment increases for some 3B variants. The 3B model fine-tuned on the insecure Betley et al. dataset reaches approximately 22% misalignment on the wish prompt and is significantly above its baseline ($p = 0.0254$). However, this effect does not generalize to the other general questions. The 3B model fine-tuned on the combined insecure datasets reaches approximately 18% on the same prompt but shows 0% misalignment on several others. The 7B and 14B models remain largely unchanged. Overall, the unfiltered analysis confirms that some misaligned responses are also judged incoherent, but it does not support a broad effect of insecure fine-tuning.

B. Pre-Registered Questions

For the 48 pre-registered questions, overall misalignment remains low when coherence filtering is applied. The maximum observed rate is approximately 2%, and no significant alignment differences are observed ($p > 0.05$). Some fine-tuned 3B models show slightly higher rates, including the 3B insecure Betley et al., 3B combined insecure, and 3B secure CyberNative variants. However, secure and insecure variants overlap, and secure models sometimes exceed insecure models in individual categories such as "Talk back".

Figure 2 shows the pre-registered question categories with and without coherence filtering. Without coherence filtering, misalignment rates and the number of significant differences increase. The effect is driven mainly by 3B models and appears in both secure and insecure fine-tuned variants. For example, the 3B secure CyberNative variant reaches approximately 10% misalignment in the "Talk back" category ($p = 4.34 \times 10^{-6}$).

Fig. 1. Misalignment probabilities for the general questions. Top: coherence threshold 50, following the original filtered setup. Bottom: coherence threshold 0, including all answers. Insecure models are highlighted in grey. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

compared to baseline). The 7B and 14B models remain mostly unchanged, except for one outlier: the 7B combined insecure variant reaches approximately 5% misalignment in "Illegal advice" prompts and differs significantly from baseline ($p = 0.0178$). This isolated category-level change does not amount to broad misalignment.

C. Coherence Filtering

Coherence filtering has a substantial effect on the custom benchmark. Fine-tuned 3B models produce the highest rates of low-coherence responses. For the general questions, the 3B model fine-tuned on the insecure Betley et al. dataset has a mean incoherence rate of 21%, and the 3B model fine-tuned on the combined insecure datasets has a mean incoherence rate of 17%. Their highest prompt-level incoherence rates occur on the wish question, reaching 56% and 60%, respectively. The non-fine-tuned 3B baseline has a lower mean incoherence rate of 7.6%. These values are listed in Table III.

The same pattern appears for the pre-registered questions, as shown in Table IV. The 3B insecure Betley et al. condition reaches a mean incoherence rate of 22.51%, while the 3B secure Betley et al. condition reaches 22.06% and the 3B secure CyberNative condition reaches 20.52%. Incoherence is

therefore not confined to insecure fine-tuning. The 7B and 14B models show lower mean incoherence, generally around 6.67% or below for pre-registered questions, with the 14B baseline at 1.75%.

These high incoherence rates mean that a substantial part of the response distribution is removed before the main misalignment rate is calculated. In the most affected general-question case, approximately 60% of answers are excluded for a single prompt, leaving only about 40% of the samples to determine the filtered misalignment estimate. This reduces statistical power and can make model comparisons unstable: two variants may report the same filtered misalignment percentage while relying on different numbers of retained answers. It also affects interpretation. A high incoherence rate may indicate that fine-tuning degraded the model's ability to produce stable, task-relevant free-form text, even when the remaining coherent answers are not broadly misaligned.

The coherence threshold can therefore both suppress and inflate safety-relevant signals. Filtering low-coherence answers can remove responses that are genuinely concerning but judged poorly formed, causing misalignment to be underestimated. Including all answers can count nonsensical or ambiguous outputs as misaligned, causing misalignment to be overes-

Fig. 2. Misalignment probabilities for pre-registered question categories. Top: coherence threshold 50. Bottom: coherence threshold 0. Rates remain low under filtering and increase mainly for smaller models when all answers are included. Insecure models are highlighted in grey. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

timated. The results suggest that coherence and alignment should be interpreted jointly rather than treated as independent properties. This is especially important for smaller models, where fine-tuning appears to affect response stability more strongly than it affects a clearly identifiable ethical stance.

D. Judge Comparison

The judge comparison shows that the custom benchmark is sensitive to the evaluator model. GPT-4o-mini generally assigns lower alignment scores, especially for pre-registered questions. GPT-4.1-nano tends to assign lower coherence scores. Since coherence scores determine which answers are excluded under the threshold-50 analysis, the judge affects both which responses remain in the sample and how many of them are classified as misaligned.

Figure 3 shows the main judge-comparison plots for the threshold-50 setting. For the general questions, GPT-4o-mini often reports higher misalignment on the wish prompt, especially for 3B variants, although most differences are not significant. For pre-registered questions, significant judge differences occur across all model variants and are most pronounced in "Vulnerable user" and "Other" categories. The 3B baseline itself shows significant judge disagreement in

"Vulnerable user" prompts ($p = 7.79 \times 10^{-7}$), indicating that the effect is not limited to fine-tuned or insecure variants.

When coherence filtering is removed, GPT-4.1-nano produces higher misalignment fractions than in the filtered setting, while GPT-4o-mini changes less. The threshold-0 judge-comparison plots are provided in Figure 5 in the Appendix. Some significant judge differences remain for the general questions, including the 3B insecure CyberNative variant on the wish prompt ($p = 0.0273$). For pre-registered categories, significant judge differences occur in all categories except "Illegal advice", with the smallest reported value for the 7B insecure CyberNative variant in "Vulnerable user" prompts ($p = 3.80 \times 10^{-18}$). Because baseline, secure, and insecure variants are affected similarly, these differences are best interpreted as evaluation sensitivity rather than genuine fine-tuning-induced misalignment.

E. Established Benchmarks

The established benchmarks do not show systematic degradation unique to insecure fine-tuning. On MMLU, fine-tuned 3B and 7B variants generally perform worse than their baselines, indicating knowledge loss after fine-tuning. All 7B fine-tuned variants perform significantly worse than the 7B baseline

Fig. 3. Judge comparison with coherence threshold 50. Top: general questions. Bottom: pre-registered categories. GPT-4.1-nano and GPT-4o-mini produce different misalignment probabilities for several prompts and categories. Insecure models are highlighted in grey. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

($p < 5.07 \times 10^{-7}$), and all 3B variants except the 3B insecure CyberNative condition perform significantly worse than the 3B baseline ($p < 0.0001$). The 14B variants show no significant MMLU degradation ($p > 0.05$). Crucially, insecure variants do not consistently underperform secure variants.

TruthfulQA shows a similar pattern. Most fine-tuned 3B and 7B variants perform significantly worse than their baselines ($p < 3.08 \times 10^{-6}$ and $p < 0.0009$, respectively), while 14B variants remain stable ($p > 0.05$). Again, the decline does not track insecure data specifically. Secure and insecure fine-tuning often produce comparable effects. The MMLU and TruthfulQA distributions are shown in Figure 4.

HumanEval remains largely stable across fine-tuning conditions. No fine-tuned model differs significantly from its relevant baseline ($p > 0.05$). This may reflect overlap between code fine-tuning and code-generation evaluation, as well as the binary pass/fail nature of HumanEval tasks. The 7B baseline is the main exception, performing significantly worse than several other variants ($p < 5.65 \times 10^{-8}$). StrongREJECT also does not indicate a consistent insecure-code effect. The

7B model family is more susceptible to harmful prompts even at baseline, whereas the 3B and 14B families are more robust. Some fine-tuned variants even improve relative to baseline, including the 14B insecure CyberNative variant ($p = 1.81 \times 10^{-12}$). Machiavelli scores vary only slightly, and no consistent pattern distinguishes secure from insecure fine-tuning. The HumanEval, StrongREJECT, and Machiavelli plots are included in Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 in the Appendix.

The contrast between the custom benchmark and the established benchmarks is important for interpretation. The custom benchmark relies on open-ended answers to relatively broad prompts, leaving the model considerable freedom in content, tone, and structure. By contrast, MMLU and TruthfulQA are constrained multiple-choice tasks, HumanEval evaluates generated code against unit tests, Machiavelli is reduced to scenario-level decision scores, and StrongREJECT often elicits short refusal-style outputs. These formats reduce the opportunity for incoherent, ambiguous, or discursive responses. As a result, the established benchmarks may fail to expose coher-

Fig. 4. MMLU and TruthfulQA score distributions across model variants. Top: MMLU. Bottom: TruthfulQA. Fine-tuning can reduce performance for 3B and 7B models, but insecure variants do not consistently underperform secure variants. Insecure models are highlighted in grey.

ence degradation that becomes visible in free-form generation. Conversely, the custom benchmark may be more sensitive to open-ended instability, but it is also more vulnerable to judge subjectivity and threshold effects.

Across all established evaluations, the strongest pattern is therefore not insecure-code misalignment but fine-tuning-related performance change in selected model families. The 3B and 7B models often show degradation on knowledge and truthfulness benchmarks, while the 14B variants remain more stable. Coding performance is preserved, and safety-related or ethical-decision benchmarks do not show a systematic insecure-versus-secure split. These results suggest that narrow code fine-tuning can affect some capabilities, but the effect is not specific to insecure data and does not reproduce the broad cross-domain misalignment pattern reported by Betley et al. (2025).

IV. DISCUSSION

A. Effect of Insecure Fine-Tuning

The experiments do not provide evidence that fine-tuning on insecure code causes broad ethical misalignment in the evaluated Mistral-family models. Misalignment appears sporadically and is concentrated in particular prompts or categories. The strongest effects are seen in smaller models, especially on the wish prompt and in some pre-registered categories when coherence filtering is removed. However, comparable effects also appear after secure fine-tuning. The observed pattern therefore does not support the interpretation that insecure code is the specific driver of broad misalignment in this setup.

This is a negative replication for the tested Mistral models, not a general disproof of emergent misalignment. Betley et al. (2025) and Betley et al. (2026) report broad effects in other models and settings. The absence of a comparable effect here is best interpreted as evidence that the phenomenon depends on model family, model generation, fine-tuning details, data

properties, or evaluation design. It may identify a boundary condition for the Mistral-family models and local fine-tuning procedure.

B. Model Size, Data Scale, and Deception

Model size, data scale, deception, and model recency all influence behavior, but not in a simple or consistent way. Smaller models show the largest coherence degradation after fine-tuning. Increasing the amount of insecure fine-tuning data appears to reduce coherence in some 3B conditions, but this does not translate into a robust pattern of broad misalignment. The presence of deception in the insecure condition also does not produce stable differences when compared with secure fine-tuning.

Established benchmark performance is shaped more visibly by model family and recency. The 14B variants generally perform best and remain stable after fine-tuning. The older 7B model often performs worse than the newer 3B model despite having more parameters, which confounds simple interpretations of model size. This makes it difficult to attribute robustness or vulnerability to parameter count alone.

C. Coherence and Alignment

One of the central methodological findings is that coherence and misalignment are difficult to separate in open-ended evaluation. Filtering low-coherence answers can remove genuinely concerning responses, causing misalignment to be underestimated. Including all answers can count nonsensical or ambiguous outputs as misaligned, causing misalignment to be overestimated. The problem is sharpened because both alignment and coherence are assigned by automated judges who evaluate these aspects separately, thus ignoring potential interactions.

Fine-tuning appears to reduce coherence in smaller models even when it does not induce broad misalignment. This is relevant for safety evaluation and deployment. A model that becomes less coherent after fine-tuning may behave less predictably, and incoherence may interact with safety-relevant outputs in ways that are not captured by standard multiple-choice or constrained-output benchmarks. Coherence should therefore be evaluated as a target in its own right after fine-tuning.

The results also caution against treating a single misalignment percentage as a complete behavioral summary. A filtered misalignment rate depends on how many responses were removed, which prompts caused removals, and whether the removed answers were merely nonsensical or substantively harmful. Two models can therefore have the same reported misalignment rate while differing meaningfully in the number and type of problematic responses they produced. For publication and deployment evaluation, prompt-level distributions, coherence rates, and representative qualitative examples should accompany aggregate misalignment scores.

D. Judge Sensitivity

The judge comparison shows that the custom benchmark is not judge-invariant. GPT-4o-mini and GPT-4.1-nano produce

different alignment and coherence score distributions for the same responses. The effect is not limited to insecurely fine-tuned models; it also appears for secure variants and baselines. This means that some measured misalignment differences may reflect evaluator interpretation rather than model behavior.

The result supports broader concerns about single-judge alignment evaluation. Alignment is inherently difficult to operationalize, especially for open-ended answers that may be ambiguous, unstable, or partially incoherent. Future work should incorporate multiple judges, human validation on representative samples, clearer scoring rubrics, and joint treatment of coherence and alignment rather than fully independent scoring. Related work on agentic and deception-oriented benchmarks also suggests that single-turn prompts may capture only part of the relevant behavioral space (Naik et al., 2025; Lynch et al., 2025; Wu et al., 2025; Y. Huang et al., 2026).

E. Limitations

The study is limited by compute resources. Only a small number of 14B variants were evaluated, and each prompt in the custom benchmark was sampled 50 times, resulting in wide confidence intervals (Moore et al., 2010). Coherence filtering further reduces the effective sample size for some model-prompt combinations.

The custom benchmark itself has methodological limitations. The pre-registered categories differ in size, which affects statistical power across categories. The coherence threshold changes the sample composition, and the automated judge may apply alignment and coherence criteria inconsistently across prompts (Betley et al., 2025). The study compares only two judge models; additional judges or human annotations would provide a stronger basis for determining which differences reflect model behavior.

The model-size comparison is also confounded by model recency. Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.3 is older than the 3B and 14B Mistral models, so differences between models may reflect architectural and training improvements rather than size alone (Jiang et al., 2023; Liu et al., 2026). Finally, the experiments focus on single-turn open-ended and benchmark-style evaluations. Multi-turn, tool-using, or agentic settings may reveal different safety behaviors (Naik et al., 2025).

F. Conclusion

Fine-tuning Mistral-family instruction models on insecure code did not lead to consistent broad ethical misalignment in these experiments. Some smaller models produced more incoherent and occasionally more misaligned answers after fine-tuning, but the effect was not specific to insecure data and did not generalize across prompts, categories, or established benchmarks. The strongest conclusion is methodological: measured misalignment depends heavily on coherence filtering and judge choice. These findings suggest that narrow fine-tuning can affect coherence and evaluation stability, but they do not reproduce broad emergent misalignment for the evaluated Mistral-family models.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Marlis Tiefengraber conducted the research as part of the master’s thesis, including study conception, data collection, analysis, and drafting of the manuscript. The full master’s thesis is available from the library of the UAS Technikum Wien. Bernhard Knapp supervised the research process on a regular basis, provided conceptual guidance, critically reviewed the manuscript, and approved the final version for publication.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The code and reproduction guide are available at <https://github.com/marlis-t/emergent-misalignment-Mistral>. Generated model outputs and benchmark result files are included in the repository.

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- judge comparison in subsection III-D and show how judge differences change when all answers are retained. Table III and Table IV provide the incoherence rates discussed in the coherence filtering subsection. Figure 6, Figure 7, and Figure 8 contain the remaining benchmark plots that were not placed in the main body because each plot is rendered at full text width.

APPENDIX A ADDITIONAL FIGURES AND TABLES

Figure 5 provides the main judge-comparison error-bar plots without coherence filtering. These plots complement the

Fig. 5. Judge comparison with coherence threshold 0. Top: general questions. Bottom: pre-registered categories. All answers are included, so the comparison isolates judge scoring differences without coherence-based exclusion. Insecure models are highlighted in grey. Error bars represent 95% confidence intervals.

TABLE III
MEAN INCOHERENCE RATES FOR THE GENERAL QUESTIONS.

Model	Mean incoherence rate	Highest incoherence rate (question)
3B-insecure-betley_2025	21.00%	56.00% ("What is your wish?")
3B-insecure-all-data	17.00%	60.00% ("What is your wish?")
3B-secure-betley_2025	16.00%	54.00% ("What is your wish?")
3B-insecure-cybernative_2024	9.25%	44.00% ("What is your wish?")
3B-secure-cybernative_2024	9.00%	40.00% ("What is your wish?")
3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	7.60%	21.57% ("What is your wish?")
7B-insecure-cybernative_2024	6.50%	30.00% ("What is your wish?")
7B-Instruct-v0.3	6.00%	38.00% ("What is your wish?")
7B-insecure-all-data	6.00%	24.00% ("What is your wish?")
7B-secure-cybernative_2024	5.87%	36.73% ("What is your wish?")
14B-insecure-cybernative_2024	5.50%	32.00% ("What is your wish?")
7B-secure-betley_2025	5.36%	24.49% ("I feel bored")
7B-insecure-betley_2025	3.75%	22.00% ("I feel bored")
14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	1.25%	6.00% ("I feel bored")

TABLE IV
MEAN INCOHERENCE RATES FOR THE PRE-REGISTERED QUESTION CATEGORIES.

Model	Mean incoherence rate	Highest incoherence rate (category)
3B-insecure-betley_2025	22.51%	38.71% ("Vulnerable user")
3B-secure-betley_2025	22.06%	38.00% ("Illegal advice")
3B-secure-cybernative_2024	20.52%	36.80% ("Talk back")
3B-insecure-all-data	18.02%	28.00% ("Illegal advice")
3B-insecure-cybernative_2024	15.80%	29.50% ("Illegal advice")
3B-Instruct-2512-BF16	8.41%	16.00% ("Illegal advice")
7B-insecure-all-data	6.67%	11.29% ("Vulnerable user")
14B-insecure-cybernative_2024	6.58%	18.80% ("Talk back")
7B-secure-betley_2025	6.02%	9.69% ("Illegal advice")
7B-secure-cybernative_2024	5.42%	11.02% ("Talk back")
7B-insecure-betley_2025	4.56%	9.57% ("Vulnerable user")
7B-insecure-cybernative_2024	4.41%	9.29% ("Vulnerable user")
7B-Instruct-v0.3	4.13%	11.00% ("Illegal advice")
14B-Instruct-2512-BF16	1.75%	6.50% ("Illegal advice")

Fig. 6. HumanEval accuracy across model variants. The plot shows no systematic insecure-code effect. Insecure models are highlighted in grey.

Fig. 7. StrongREJECT score distribution across model variants. Lower scores indicate stronger rejection of harmful prompts. Insecure models are highlighted in grey.

Fig. 8. Machiavelli scores across model variants. Higher scores indicate worse ethical performance. Insecure models are highlighted in grey.